

INTEGRATION FACTORS IN STRENGTHENING PEACE AND STABILITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, the spiritual, moral and cultural development of the society, the development of the social development the new Uzbekistan and the processes of consolidation of peace and stability, of course, have a unique partnership with the neighboring countries. In this regard, turning Central Asia into a region of peace, sustainable development and good neighborliness is defined as a priority direction of foreign policy. For example, it was highlighted that the formation of security, stability, harmonious neighborhood environment in the vicinity of Uzbekistan was strengthened as a priority task in the near future.

Key words: social development, social structure, stability, spiritual and moral, cultural development, spiritual values, national idea, cultural heritage, history of statehood, science and enlightenment, innovation, intellectual work, science, education, common tradition and customs, single history.

Introduction

One of the most important issues that concerns the international community and all of humanity today is the issue of peace and security, ensuring peace, security, and stability throughout the world. In the current conditions of all countries, it is crucial to take effective measures to strengthen peace and stability. If any violation of peace occurs, it may lead to a local conflict escalating into a global nuclear war. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's participation in the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly and the efforts undertaken to ensure security, socio-economic development, and strengthen regional cooperation in Central Asia are among the important practical steps taken in this direction. More than 500 participants, including leaders of Central Asian states, influential official delegations from the UN, EU, ASEAN, SCO, CSTO, OIC, ECO, as well as over 100 renowned international experts and leading foreign media representatives, including diplomats accredited in Uzbekistan, took part in this significant international event. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev participated in the forum and gave a speech. The head of our state spoke about the active foreign policy that is being implemented to achieve peace and sustainable development in Central Asia, the important tasks of ensuring security in the region, and put forward a number of relevant initiatives.

Turning Central Asia into a region of peace, sustainable development and good neighborliness has been defined by our President as a priority of Uzbekistan's foreign policy. This is reflected in the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. For example, in this programmatic document, the formation of security, stability, harmonious neighborhood environment in the vicinity of Uzbekistan is confirmed as a priority task in the near future. Peaceful, economically developed

Central Asia is the most important goal and main task that Uzbekistan is striving for. The countries of Central Asia are not only geographically and geopolitically close to each other, but are also a single place of culture and civilization. The peoples living here have a common spiritual-moral values, common traditions and customs, common history binds.

The region, located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, has been a place for communication between world cultures, languages and religions for thousands of years. Today, Uzbekistan is conducting an active and pragmatic policy based on the principles of close neighborliness and friendship. Due to the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, cooperation relations with the countries of the region in the political, trade-economic, transport-logistics and cultural-humanitarian spheres are rapidly developing. As a result of the head of state's state and practical visits to neighboring countries, as well as regular dialogues with the leaders of neighboring countries within the framework of various international summits, a fundamentally new political environment has been created in Central Asia in the past short period of time. The number of strategic partner countries has expanded.

The development of the social development of the new Uzbekistan and the processes of consolidation of peace and stability, of course, have a unique partnership with the neighboring countries. In this regard, turning Central Asia into a region of peace, stable development and good neighborliness has been defined by our President as a priority of Uzbekistan's foreign policy.

For example, the formation of security, stability, harmonious neighborhood environment in the vicinity of Uzbekistan has been established as a priority task in the near future. Peaceful, economically developed Central Asia is the most important goal and main task that Uzbekistan is striving for. The countries of Central Asia are not only geographically and geopolitically close to each other, but are also a single place of culture and civilization. People living here are connected by common spiritual and moral values, common traditions and customs, common history.

Today, Uzbekistan is conducting an active and pragmatic policy based on the principles of close neighborliness and friendship. Thanks to the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, cooperation relations with the countries of the region in the political, trade-economic, transport-logistics and cultural-humanitarian spheres are rapidly developing today. Uzbekistan takes a pragmatic approach to solving the most sensitive issues with the countries of the region, especially regarding the delimitation and demarcation of state borders, reaching historic agreements. For example, an agreement was signed on about 85 percent of the Uzbek-Kyrgyz state border. In the words of the President, the parties have shown their political will and readiness to make mutually acceptable decisions, and for the first time in a long time, progress has been made on this sensitive issue. As a result of the resumption of the activity of checkpoints at the borders with neighboring countries, ease of movement of the population is being created. It is not an exaggeration to say that this is a great service for the establishment of contacts with relatives and relatives in neighboring countries, and another important aspect is the development of mutual trade.

In today's time, the concepts of sustainable development and security cannot be imagined separately. The fact that relations between neighboring countries are expanding at the level of the border regions, and the mechanisms of public diplomacy are being actively used are enriching the relations of the countries of the region. Special emphasis is placed on

expanding cooperation between legislative bodies, and inter-parliamentary friendship groups are being formed.

“ Stability and security are the decisive factors of the development of every country and the investment attractiveness of its economy”¹. “Like all humanity, every nation and nation in the world strives towards the dawn of its development. As beautiful and attractive as the sun, which is a great phenomenon of nature, appears to the world every morning, the beginning of new mornings in the development of peoples and countries of the world is so blessed and refreshing. From this point of view, there are periods of fundamental renewal in the history of nations, in which the genius of a particular nation, its desire to manifest its potential, and creative activity reach the highest peaks”².

Respecting the languages, customs and traditions of the nationalities and peoples living in the territory of Uzbekistan, enlightening their views on the legal, socio-cultural and political foundations related to the spirit of the time from a socio-philosophical point of view, and in the social and political life of all the representatives of all nationalities and peoples. It is important to consider the dialectical connection of differential approaches and socio-mental characteristics of bilateral participation and formation of the environment and opportunities. Every nation, nation and people, every social system and state lives on the basis of certain principles and values and acts in pursuit of its interests, dreams, goals and aspirations. Each nation and nation develops and progresses based on certain ideas and ideologies in its historical social development. In our country, which aims to build a free, democratic society based on social cooperation, the national ideology unites all layers of the population and calls for action towards a common goal. In such an ideology, not conflicting aspects, but universal principles are strengthened. Any ideology sets specific goals for itself. These goals determine the ways and means of achieving the final result.

“The international community of Uzbekistan, first and foremost, aims to strengthen friendly relations and cooperation with neighboring states, based on mutual support, collaboration, security, and stability, along with the development and enhancement of social, ethical, and cultural values”³. It encompasses nurturing societal development, promoting spiritual and moral principles, preserving national heritage and cultural legacy, safeguarding the historical and contemporary traditions of the Uzbek people and their statehood, ensuring the comprehensiveness and continuity of education, and cultivating the upbringing of a progressive generation.

“Human beings are inherently endowed with constant possibilities for creating new forms. To express their emotions, they resort to language or utilize the food accepted by society. We cannot fully convey our emotions to one another without translating our sensations into a known form.

We continuously change the forms of our cultural identity - these are the changes that the customs and trends of the era exert on us. We constantly modify our forms, accepting them from our ancestors in a hereditary style, and these changes shape our way of life”⁴. In reality, in unchanging things, we do not see the impact of vitality and we modify them ourselves. Especially young people perceive this as normal: they try to adapt unique actions -

¹ <https://religions.uz/news/detail?id=634>

² Mirziyoev Sh.M. Development strategy of new Uzbekistan. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 2022. - B. 4.

³ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Introduction. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 2023. - B.3.

⁴ Robert Greene. 48 rules of authority. -Tashkent: "Info Capital Books" 2022. - B.684.

various fashions - through the fog of different attire. Different attire governs changing forms, specifically managing the vital strength. The formation of the nation carries significant importance in terms of spiritual factors, as it provides the opportunity for the perpetuity of the nation's eternal existence. These factors are considered essential conditions for the progress of the nation. In fact, the main factor in ensuring the nation's perpetuity and its stability is its internal spiritual capacity.

"To preserve social and political stability, especially in difficult times, it serves as the basis for implementing a clear policy aimed at the long-term progress of the state. This, in turn, is the main condition for deciding on national sovereignty, strengthening international relations, and attracting wide-scale foreign investments into the developing economy"⁵. The capability, talent, diligence, and independent work of nations, together with the material and spiritual culture of modern civilization, have paved the way and methods for their development and advancement. According to experts, there are nearly three thousand nations on Earth. They form 96 percent of humanity, while only 4 percent are states and nationalities. The population of each nation ranges from several thousand to several hundred million.

Therefore, in the present, society's development and finding the most reasonable paths are of interest to everyone, and it is the responsibility of everyone. Thus, it is natural for different proposals to emerge regarding the ways to solve each problem. The goal is to find the most reasonable way to solve a specific problem.

In today's society and states where there is no mutual competition between political groups, parties, and classes, it is possible for democracy to flourish. Independent Uzbekistan is in such a state. It is developing based on the principles of democracy and the rule of law.

"The majority of the country's multi-ethnic population has accepted the idea of Uzbekistan as a great state in the future. The chosen reforms will be implemented with determination."⁶

The idea of national independence cannot be achieved by defining "aggressive nationalism," "nationalism," and "national discrimination" with the goals of "great state chauvinism" and "cosmopolitanism." Instead, it is necessary to strive for "national patriotism," "national unity," "national solidarity," "international cooperation," "friendship," and "mutual understanding among nations."

The concept of "opposing ideas with ideas, opposing ignorance with knowledge" holds great significance. When it comes to international relations, understanding each other's culture, customs, and religious beliefs, respecting each other, working together towards common goals, and promoting cooperation is crucial.

Conclusion. the above mentioned ideas emphasize the importance of national identity, mutual respect and cooperation in our society. National identity and mutual respect are the foundation of a new social development in Uzbekistan, which reflects the spiritual values of the people and contributes to the achievement of the country's goals.

The concept of "national identity" is especially important for multi-ethnic Uzbekistan, where various nationalities live together. It helps to unite different nationalities and promote the

⁵ I. Karimov. Threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development of Uzbekistan at the threshold of the 21st century. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 1997. - B.290.

⁶ I. Karimov. Threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development of Uzbekistan at the threshold of the 21st century. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" 1997. - B.293

common goals and interests of each nationality, while also playing a crucial role in building a free and democratic society in the new Uzbekistan.

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